

Spectrophotometric Determination of Ionization Constants of Substituted Naphthols in 50% v/v Acetone-Water Mixture

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The ionization constants of substituted naphthols were determined by spectrophotometric method in 50% v/v acetone-water mixture at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ and zero ionic strength. The pK_a values are in the following order.

2-Acetyl 1-naphthol > 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde > 1-hydroxy naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid (Na-salt) > 2-nitroso 1-naphthol > 1-hydroxy 2-nitrosonephthalene 4-sulphonic acid > 2-nitro 1-naphthol. The ir. spectra of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol, 2-nitroso 1-naphthol and 2-nitro 1-naphthol was recorded and the variation of ionization constants is discussed in terms of relative strengths of hydrogen bond.

AMONGST the various physico-chemical methods used in determining ionization constants and the chelate stability constants, the potentiometric and the spectrophotometric methods are the most versatile ones. Some of the orthosubstituted naphthols like 2-nitroso 1-naphthol, 1-nitroso 2-naphthol, 2-acetyl 1-naphthol and 1-hydroxy 2-nitroso naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid have been widely used as chelating agents and their chelate stability constants were determined by potentiometric method¹⁻⁵. The presence of intramolecular hydrogen bond affects the pK_a value of the dissociable proton of an organic compound. In continuation of our earlier work⁶, the present study was undertaken with a view to discuss the variation of ionization constants of substituted naphthols in terms of relative strengths of hydrogen bond.

Materials and Methods: The compounds 2-acetyl 1-naphthol (m.p. 102°) and 2-nitro 1-naphthol (m.p. 128°) of high degree of purity was prepared by literature methods^{7,8}. 2-Hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde, 2-nitroso 1-naphthol and 1-hydroxy naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid (Na-salt) were obtained from Fluka Company. All other chemicals were of A. R. grade.

An Elico pH meter model LI-10 with elico glass and calomel electrodes, capable of reading upto ± 0.02 pH was employed for the pH measurements. The pH meter was standardised with buffers of pH 4.00 and 9.00. A Spekol spectrophotometer was used for recording the optical density of solutions in the visible range. Perkin Elmer 137 Infra-cord was used to record spectra in the frequency range 800 to 400 cm^{-1} . The instrument was calibrated using polystyrene film.

The experimental method consists in the first step, the selection of the wave length at which the absorbance is minimum in the pH region where the substance is in the unionized state and maximum in the pH region in which the substance is completely in the ionized state. Later in the actual titration 100 ml. of a definite

concentration ($X \times 10^{-3}\text{ M}$) of the ligand solution was taken in 50% v/v acetone-water mixture to which 1 ml. of 0.1 M HCl was added and titrated against 0.1 M NaOH using pH meter and spectrophotometer. The optical density (A) of the solution at different pH values were recorded at the selected wavelength, by transferring an aliquot quantity of the solution into the cuvette. The total concentration of the acid was kept constant by transferring the solution taken in the cuvette back to the beaker. To avoid the erroneous readings from the previous residues the cuvette was rinsed with the solution taken in the beaker and the rinsings were returned back to the beaker. Thus obtained, optical density values at different pH values were corrected for volume changes. All measurements were done at $30^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$. From the maxima, in the plots of $\Delta A/\Delta \text{pH}$ against pH, the pK_a values for different acids were obtained. Thus obtained pK_a values are corrected to zero ionic strength using the relation

$$pK_a = pK'_a + \frac{0.51 \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}{1 + \mu^{\frac{1}{2}}}$$

TABLE I—THE SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION OF IONIZATION CONSTANTS OF SUBSTITUTED NAPHTHOLS IN 50% ACETONE-WATER MIXTURE AT 30° AND ZERO IONIC STRENGTH.

Name of the Acid	$pK_a - \text{OH} \pm 0.02$	$-\text{OH cm}^{-1}$
1. 2-Acetyl 1-naphthol.	10.4 10.72*	3400
2. 2-Hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde.	10.02	3450
3. 1-Hydroxy naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid (Na-salt).	9.8 9.81*	3600
4. 2-Nitroso 1-naphthol.	8.10 8.16*	3160
5. 1-Hydroxy 2-nitrosonephthalene 4-sulphonic acid.	7.06 7.16*	3380
6. 2-Nitro 1-naphthol.	6.72 6.76*	3250

*Potentiometric values at 35° and $\mu=0.1\text{M KNO}_3$

where pK_a is the ionization constant at zero ionic strength, pK'_a the apparent or measured ionization constant and μ , the ionic strength of the mixture. The ionization constants thus determined are recorded in Table 1. The ir spectra of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol, 2-nitroso 1-naphthol, 2-nitro 1-naphthol and 1-hydroxy 2-nitroso naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid was recorded in Nujol mull.

Results and Discussions

The ionization constant of hydroxyl group of substituted naphthols in 50% V/V acetone-water mixture at zero ionic strength and at 30° are presented in Table-1. The pK_a values of phenolic proton are in the following order.

2-Acetyl 1-naphthol > 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde > 1-hydroxy naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid (Na-salt) > 2-nitroso 1-naphthol > 1-hydroxy 2-nitroso naphthalene 4-sulphonic acid > 2-nitro 1-naphthol.

An examination of the infrared spectrum of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol indicates that the band at 3500 cm^{-1} due to the free OH is absent and in its place a broad band with its centre at 3400 cm^{-1} is present. This may be attributed to the intramolecular hydrogen bonding of naphthoic-OH with the oxygen of the acetyl group in ortho position. Thus the shift of 200 cm^{-1} in the present investigation is more than the shift of 10 cm^{-1} observed by Patil and Sen⁹ in the case of 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde. This indicates that the intramolecular hydrogen bonding in 2-acetyl 1-naphthol is stronger than 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde. As a result the pK_a value of hydroxyl group of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol is greater than that of 2-hydroxy 1-naphthaldehyde.

The broad band present at 3160 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum of 2-nitroso 1-naphthol can be attributed to the hydrogen bonded hydroxyl group. Amstutz, Hunsbarger and Chessick¹⁰ observed a band at 3240 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectra of 1-nitro 2-naphthol which they have attributed to the hydrogen bonding. The band at 3250 cm^{-1} in case of 2-nitro 1-naphthol indicates that the hydrogen bond is weaker than that of 2-nitroso 1-naphthol. The weaker H-bond in 2-nitro 1-naphthol is due to the fact that the oxygen of a resonating nitro group is a weaker basic centre than

the oxygen of the nitroso group. Hence the pK_a value is less than that of 2-nitroso 1-naphthol. A shift of hydroxy band by 220 cm^{-1} in 1-hydroxy 2-nitrosonephthalene 4-sulphonic acid indicates the presence of a weaker hydrogen bond when compared to 2-nitroso 1-naphthol. This is due to the presence of electron withdrawing inductive effect of sulphonic acid group, hence the pK_a value is less than that of 2-nitroso 1-naphthol.

To obtain some more information the infrared spectra of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol, 2-nitro 1-naphthol, 2-nitroso 1-naphthol and 1-hydroxy 2-nitrosonephthalene 4-sulphonic acid were recorded in solutions of CCl_4 . The OH bands in saturated solutions of 2-acetyl 1-naphthol, 2-nitro 1-naphthol, 2-nitroso 1-naphthol and 1-hydroxy 2-nitrosonephthalene 4 sulphonic acid in CCl_4 are generally weak and located at 3400 cm^{-1} , 3250 cm^{-1} , 3200 cm^{-1} and 3200 cm^{-1} respectively.

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References

1. G. L. VAN UITERT and W. C. FERNELIUS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, **76**, 375.
2. S. A. BAJUE, C. A. TAYLOR and G. C. LALOR, *Revista Latinoamericana de quimica.*, 1971, p. 102.
3. C. M. CALLAHAN, W. C. FERNELIUS and B. P. BLOCK, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1957, **16**, 101.
4. P. LINGAIAH and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1972, **10**, 670.
5. P. LINGAIAH and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1974, **12**, 539.
6. P. LINGAIAH and E. V. SUNDARAM, *Current Sci.*, 1974, **43**, 343.
7. STROUGHTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **57**, 202.
8. O. HOFFMAN, *Ber.*, 1885, **18**, 46.
9. J. N. PATIL and D. N. SEN, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **50**, 413.
10. E. D. AMSTUTZ, I. M. HUNSBERGER and J. J. CHESSICK, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 1220.